

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI TIZIMLASHTIRILGAN TAHDIDLAR.....	40
Qodirov Tuyg'un Uzoqovich, Nabiyev Bexzod Shavkatovich	
SANOAT TARMOQLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSIYA VA TEXNOLOGIK MODERNIZATSIYANING O'RNI	44
Boboqulov Sanjar Bahromqulovich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIYOTI VA UNING SOLIQ TIZIMIDA QO'LLANILISHI	49
To'xtabayev Oybek Odilovich	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH BO'YICHA ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR.....	56
Ismailov Bobir Salomovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY JIHATLARI	62
Yangiboyev F.B.	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY SALOHİYATDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	68
Turayev Og'abek Kaxramonovich	
XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAJRIBASI.....	75
Yusupova Feruza Yo'ldoshevna	
BANK XIZMATLARI SIFATINI BOSHQARISHNING INTEGRATSION VA ADAPTIV MODEL.....	83
Ibroximov Ilxomjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLAR ASOSIDA BAHOLASH	89
Qidirniyazov Ajiniyaz Sherniyazovich	
ICHKI NAZORAT VA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDAGI XAVFLARNI BOSHQARISH	94
Islamova Nargiza Mirzaxidovna	
TURIZMNING MINTAQADA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI	104
Rasulova Muxabbat Teshabayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH ORQALI INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING HOZIRGI KUNDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	111
Begamov S.X.	
RETHINKING JOB CREATION: ONTOLOGICAL AND EPISTEMOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MACROECONOMIC EMPLOYMENT ANALYSIS.....	116
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
HUDUDIY TURIZM KLASTERLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA ULARNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	125
Ro'zimova Xusnora Mirzobek qizi	
SUG'URTACHILIK VA O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA SEKTORINING HOLATI.....	129
O'runboyeva Sotima Alisher qizi	
GO'SHT VA GO'SHT MAHSULOTLARINI SANOAT USULIDA QAYTA ISHLASHDA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI.....	134
Xaydarova Sitora Suranbay qizi	
KORXONALAR QIYMATINI BAHOLASH VA BOZOR BAHOSINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	139
Abduraxmanov Sherzodbek Ravshanovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIK VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK UYG'UNLIGI.....	145
Jamaldinova Asalxon Saliyevna	
2025-YILDA O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN ENG YAXSHI 10 TA TRANSPORT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA INNOVATSIYALARI	151
Mamasaliyeva Mukaddas Ibadullayevna, Beketov Timur Kazakbayevich	

MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHNING INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN YONDASHUVLARI: AN'ANAVIY VA ZAMONAVIY TIZIMLAR QIYOSIY TAHLILI	155
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННО-ИНВЕСТИЦИОННАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ В НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ	163
Хайдарова Ёркиной Аскар кизи	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA INNOVATSION TADBIRKORLIKNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING FISKAL VA INSTITUTSIONAL MEKANIZMLARI	170
Mamatova Nodira Mirzavaliyevna	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА И УСТОЙЧИВЫЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИИ: ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ МОДЕЛИ ПЕРЕХОДА ТЕПЛИЧНЫХ ХОЗЯЙСТВ ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ АГЛОМЕРАЦИИ НА СОЛНЕЧНЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ ЭНЕРГОСНАБЖЕНИЯ	178
Срожиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна, Абдувалиева Зилола Абдуллаевна	
МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	186
Yuldashova Nilufar Ziyabayevna	
RIVOJLANISHDA RAQOBAT EMAS, BALKI HAMKORLIKNING USTUVORLIGI: NAZARIY VA AMALIY TAHLIL	190
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich	
IJTIMOY HIMOYA QAMROVINI KENGAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI VA "QAMRAB OLINMAGAN O'RTA QATLAM" MUAMMOSI	196
Bafoev Farrux Jo'raqulovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA EKOLOGIK BOSHQARUVNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	202
Shanazarova Gulyoraxon Baxtiyarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON STARTAP EKOTIZIMIDA INVESTITSIYA JALB QILISH JARAYONINING INSTITUTSIONAL MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH MEKANIZMLARI	208
Xoliqova Xurshidaxon Xayotjon qizi	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SHAROITIDA STARTAP EKOTIZIMINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLTLARI	214
Usmanov Gafurjon Shavkatovich	
QURILISHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA SIFATNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHI	220
Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSION MUHITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING STRATEGIYALARI	225
Xolov Sherali Axrorboyevich	
2010-2024-YILLARDA O'ZBEKISTONDA TO'QIMACHILIKNI INVESTITSIYALASHNING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI	229
Ashurov Shuhratbek Qudrat o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI	233
Sherbekova Kamola Norbekovna	
AHOLI MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGI DARAJASI VA UNI BAHOLASHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	243
Abduvoxidov Akmal Abdulazizovich	
MARKAZIY BANK KURS SIYOSATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	249
Saydullayev Nodirbek Narzullaevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MINTAQALARIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SALOHİYATI VA MUAMMOLARI	258
Raupov Shuxrat Soyibovich	
ЭКОТУРИЗМ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ	264
Абидова Дилфуза Игамбердиевна, Рахматуллаева Зулайхо Хасан кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: BUSINESS CHANGE IN THE REGIONS	270
Abdullayev Muzaffar Abdujabbarovich	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIK MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLASHDA IOT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	273
Mirzaev Dilshod Artikovich	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ СТАРТАП-ПРОЕКТОВ В ВУЗАХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	279
Касимова Наргиза Сабитджановна	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	284
Ismoyilova Mahliyo Oybek qizi	
BOSHQARUVDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR (OLIV TA'LIM MISOLIDA).....	289
Kariyeva Gulnora Abdullayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORPORATIV MIJOZLARGA XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI VA ASOSIY TENDENSIYALARI.....	295
Qurbonov Odilbek Ro'zmatovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SPORT FEDERATSIYALARI VA ASSOTSIATSIYALARINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'LLARI.....	302
Umed Farmonkulovich Radjabov	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA QARATILGAN IQTISODIY MEKANIZMNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ULARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI.....	307
Mullayeva Mexrangiz Axtam qizi	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	313
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Muradova Nazira Raximjanovna	
RAQAMLI MARKETING VA ONLAYN PLATFORMALAR ORQALI EKOTURISTIK MAJMUALARNI OMMALASHTIRISH TRENDI.....	318
Xolmatova Parvina Asliddin qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGI STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI VA ULARNI YECHIMLAR.....	323
Normurzayev Umid Xolmurzayevich	
РАЗВИТИЕ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО БАНКОВСКОГО ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА КАК ФАКТОР РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	327
Бахтиёров Худайберган Хамдам угли	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLARDA TRANSFERTLARGA QARAMLIK DARAJASINI BAHOLASH (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	335
Xudoyqulov Hamidjon Abdullayevich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI.....	342
Tajibaev Berdax Asqarbay uli	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI JADALLASHTIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	347
Ashurova Maftuna Ortiq qizi	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING CAPITAL EFFICIENCY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS: DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT INTEGRATION.....	352
Sadullaeva Mokhinur Aziz kizi	
TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT AND SME INTERNATIONALIZATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW.....	358
Abduxafizova Madinabonu Mirabbos qizi	
TA'LIM SIFATINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USULLARI.....	363
Mamadiyarov Zokir Toshmurovich	
SMART UNIVERSITET KONSEPSIYASI ASOSIDA REYTING VA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI INTEGRAL BOSHQARISH.....	371
Xudoyqulov Husen Ahadovich	

BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING MILLIY VA XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOT 1-SHAKLINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI	379
Shodiyev Murodjon Bakirovich	
SUG'URTA BOZORINING RAQAMLI RIVOJLANISHIDA NAZARIY QARASHLAR	384
G'oziyeva Aziza Abdusalomovna	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA INNOVATSION LOYIHALAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI	389
Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLAR DAROMADLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	397
P.SH.Usmonov	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА МЕТОДОВ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОГО АНАЛИЗА ДЛЯ ОЦЕНКИ ДОХОДНОСТИ АКЦИЙ УЗБЕКСКИХ ЭМИТЕНТОВ.....	401
Ирмухамедова Муслима Дилшодовна	
KORXONA VA TASHKILOTLARDA INSON KAPITALIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHDA KORPORATIV MADANIYAT, AXLOQIY-RUHIY VA MA'NAVIY MUHITNING O'RNI	407
Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich, Qodirov Tuyg'un Uzoqovich	
ELEKTRON PULLARNING MOHIYATI VA ULARNING MILLIY TO'LOV TIZIMIDAGI ROLI.....	416
Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA UY XO'JALIKLARINING TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KENGAYTIRISH.....	423
Eshbaeva Shahnoza Faxriddinovna	
APPLICATION OF EXTREME MODELS IN ASSESSING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF AN ENTERPRISE	428
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGIDA XORIJIY TAJRIBA HAMDA UNI O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'LLASH SAMARADORLIGI.....	435
Bozorova Ozoda Raximovna	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATI IMIJINI OSHIRISHDAGI MUAMMOLARNI HAL ETISHDA XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI: QIYOSIY TAHLIL.....	439
Bekmurodov Navruz Ergashevich	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI SOHASIDA YARATILGAN YALPI QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT DINAMIKASI VA UNI BOSHQARISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	449
O'rinov Komiljon Kozimovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHNING MINTAQAVIY OMILLARI.....	453
Salomat Norova	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI BOZORI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	459
Usubjonov Zaxriddin Vasliddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA EKSPORT OPERATSIYALARINI SUG'URTA QILISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	465
Xalikov R. B.	
BIZNES JARAYONLAR AUTSORSINGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH USULLARI TAHLILI	472
Uzaqov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
DAVLAT MOLIVAVIY BOSHQARUVI SAMARADORLIGINING IJTIMOY ADOLATGA TA'SIRINING PEFA VA CEQ METODOLOGIYALARI ORQALI TAHLILI	477
Zokirjonov Muhammadsodiq Ravshanbek o'g'li	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA ICHKI AUDIT XIZMATINI TASHKIL QILISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	485
Turmanqulov Norpo'lat Sa'dullayevich	
MINTAQADA IJTIMOY HIMOYA TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH.....	491
Saparov Ismat Chorshanbiyevich	
MINTAQANI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDA EKOLOGIK INNOVATSIYALARNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH YO'NALISHLARI	495
Ismatov Sharofiddin Asatulloevich	

THE ESSENCE OF THE OPTIMAL COST STRATEGY	500
Sodiqov Mirakhror Abbos ugli	
TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TOG'-KURORT ZONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY JIHATLARI (CHORVOQ ERKIN TURISTIK ZONASI MISOLIDA)	504
Shomurodova Shahnoza G'ayratovna	
ICHKI AUDIT SIFATI VA SAMARADORLIGI TUSHUNCHALARINING IQTISODIY MAZMUNI HAMDA ULARNING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGI	509
Ergashev Olloyor Furqat o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARI FAOLIYATINI SOLIQQA TORTISH VA UNI HISOBINI YURITISH.....	517
Abdullayev Abdurauf	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING RISKLARINI BAHOLASHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	522
Kudaybergenova Guzal Kuanishbayevna	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KORRUPSIYAVIY-KOMPLAENS MUAMMOLARI: TAHLIL VA YECHIMLAR.....	527
Yunusov Baxtiyor Shavkatovich	
MAISHIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNING SIFAT NAZORATINI HAMDA TASHKILIIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	532
Meliyev X.T.	
ОЦЕНКА КАЧЕСТВА СЕРВИСА И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ОПРОСА.....	541
Усманова Азиза Баходировна	
RAQAMLI BANK XIZMATLARI ORQALI MOLIVAVIY INKLYUZIVLIKNI KENGAYTIRISH.....	545
Azlarova Mushtariybegim Abror qizi	
QURILISH KORXONALARNI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI	550
Egamov Raxmatillo Mirolimovich, Bobobekov Davron Gafurovich	
FINANCIAL MARKET PARTICIPANTS: A CLASSIFICATION BY ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITY.....	553
Khotamkulova Madina	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ «ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ МАХАЛЛИ» КАК ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНОГО МЕХАНИЗМА РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В СФЕРЕ ГОСТЕВЫХ ДОМОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	559
Иргашева Нигина Салохиддиновна	
BANKLARDA KREDIT GAROVI BILAN ISHLASHNING XORIJ ILG'OR TAJRIBASI VA UNDAN O'ZBEKISTON BANKLARI AMALIYOTIDA FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	567
Sh. Saidov	
MILLIY UGLEROD SAVDOSI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	573
Islamov Shoxzod Shuxrat o'g'li	
THE NECESSITY OF CREATING A BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT AND ITS ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	582
Amanov Davron Ravshan ugli	
SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI	588
Saidov Muhammadali Hakimovich, Mahammatov Hoshim, Esanbekov Diyorbek	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЁТА БАНКОВ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО И ПРИНЦИПАМИ ESG.....	595
Насирдинов Шарифджон Изатуллоевич	
ОЦЕНКА ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОБУСА.....	600
Мухитдинов Акмал Анварович, Касимов Омил Камалович, Саидов Азамат Илхом угли	
XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR ASOSIDA DUKKAKLI DON MAHSULOTLARINI YETISHTIRISHNI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH YO'NALISHLARI (HINDISTON TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA).....	608
Mirsayd Xudaybergenov	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLINING FAROVONLIGI VA DAROMAD MANBALARINI STATISTIK TAHLILI	612
Mamatkulov Baxtiyor Xalmuradovich	

KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	618
<i>Muxamedjanova Maxfuza Baxodir qizi</i>	
MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARNING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, MAZMUNI HAMDA KLASSIFIKATSIYASI.....	627
<i>Odiljonova Oybarchin Fayzullo qizi</i>	
XALQARO MOLIYA INSTITUTLARI ORQALI MAMLAKATIMIZ LOYIHALARINI AMALGA OSHIRISH TARTIBI TAHLILI.....	631
<i>Rasulova Dilfuza Valiyevna</i>	
HUDUDNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA IQTISODIY SALOHİYATNING O'RNI	636
<i>Avazbek Xalbekov</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SABZAVOTCHILIK TARMOG'INING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	642
<i>Sobir Xasanov</i>	
IMPACT OF REGIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND NATURAL RESOURCE UTILIZATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECOLOGICAL TOURISM (A DISTRICT-LEVEL ANALYSIS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION, UZBEKISTAN)	650
<i>Toyirova Shohista Bobobekovna</i>	
INNOVASION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI	657
<i>Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna</i>	
BOZOR BEQARORLIGI SHAROITIDA BANK OBRO'SINI STRATEGIK RESURS SIFATIDA BARQARORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	661
<i>Yuldasheva Kamola Qosimjonovna, Ziyeva Muhtasar Mansurdjanovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT PENSIYA TIZIMINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	667
<i>Pardayev Farrux Muzaffarovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMASIYA SHAROITIDA MENEJERLARNING RAQAMLI KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	671
<i>Sharipova Zulfiya Shokirjonovna</i>	
FUQAROLAR ISHTIROKIGA ASOSLANGAN TASHABBUSLI BUDJETLASHTIRISH TIZIMI VA UNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	677
<i>Shukurova Parizod, Soatova Nodira Boboxonovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ HUDUDLARINING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARIDA QISHLOQ TURIZMI VA EKOTURIZM – ASOSIY USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	682
<i>Abduraxmanova Aqida Fayzulla qizi</i>	
KORXONALARDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLARNING SHAFFOFLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING ROLI	691
<i>Alimbay Shamshetov</i>	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA YASHIL INVESTITSIYALARNING MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZMLARI	694
<i>Saule Ibragimova</i>	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF ELECTRICITY GENERATION BY WIND POWER PLANTS.....	698
<i>Saidov Mash'al Samadovich</i>	
TRANSFORMING TOURISM EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: AN INSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS OF PERSONNEL TRAINING SYSTEMS.....	706
<i>Abdullakhujaev Abdukodirkhuja, Ochilova Hilola Farmonovna</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLAR AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	713
<i>Elomonov Dadaxon Ozodullayevich</i>	
MAHALLIY BOSHQARUVDA YETAKCHILIK KONSEPSIYASI ORQALI FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH (FARG'ONA VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	718
<i>Siddikov Abdusalom Abdumalikovich</i>	

NEW ECONOMIC PHENOMENA: FINANCING CONSUMPTION AND SAVINGS IN THE TRANSITION TO AN EXPECTATION ECONOMY.....	724
Isomov Bekmurod Sayfiddinovich	
XIZMAT KO'TSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK YO'NALISHIDA INSTITUTSIONAL O'ZGARISHLARNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING OBYEKTIV ZARURIYATI.....	730
Sh.A.Sultonov	
MINTAQALARNING INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLARI VA ULARNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	737
Qobilov Anvar Eshpo'latovich	
KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	741
Madraimova Marxamat Raximberganovna	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТСКО-РЕКРЕАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНА.....	748
Усманова Зумрад Исламовна	
TITLE: PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP AS A MECHANISM FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN.....	753
Suxrobbek M. Salayev	
XORAZM VILOYATI TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATIDAGI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI BAHOLASH VA UNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	761
Urunov Farrux Shanazarovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT AUDITI TIZIMINING STRATEGIK TRANSFORMATSIYASI: INSTITUTSIONAL ISLOHOTLAR VA RAQAMLI MONITORINGNING STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI.....	765
Turabov Baxodir To'xtamishovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA BANDLIKNING 2025-2030-YILLARDAGI PROGNOZ PARAMETRLARI.....	770
N.I. Shermamatova	
BO'SH TURGAN DAVLAT KO'CHMAS MULK OBYEKTLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNI TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATLI JIHATLARI (O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA).....	776
Sanjarov Zuxriddin Dilshod o'g'li, Astonaqulov Muzaffar Muxsin o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING RESURS BAZASI BARQARORLIGINI TAVSIFLOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR.....	781
Bolibekov Shahboz Baxodir o'g'li	
MOLIYA-KREDIT JARAYONLARI: INVESTITSION FAOLLIKNI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMI SIFATIDA.....	787
Madaminov In'omjon Ozodovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	792
Karimov Islombek Bekpo'lat o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIMDA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI SAMARADORLIGI.....	798
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
XUSUSIY MAKTABLARNING BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI QAROR QABUL TIZIMLARI VA O'RGANUVCHI ANALITIKASI YORDAMIDA YANGILASHNING YO'LLARI	802
Esanova Shohida	
MOLIYA BOZORIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ISLOMIY MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	812
Abduraxmanova Matluba Maxamadaminovna	
KORXONALARDA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'LLARI	819
Mirzaev Ozod Furkatovich	
ЛЕКСИЧЕСКАЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ КОМПОНЕНТ ПРОДУКТИВНОЙ ПИСЬМЕННОЙ РЕЧИ.....	824
Киличева Феруза Бешимовна	
MODERN MECHANISMS FOR MONITORING REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL ECONOMY	828
Karimova Shirin Zokhid qizi	

АЛЬТЕРНАТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ КРЕДИТНОГО СКОРИНГА ДЛЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ БЕЗ БАНКОВСКОЙ ИСТОРИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	833
Шухратова Мадинабону Икром кизи	
SHAHAR EKOLOGIYASI: SHAHAR EKOTIZIMLARI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH	841
Erkiniva Mukarram Olimjon qizi	
CHAKANA SAVDO XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATUVCHI KORXONALARDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	845
Abdug'aniyev Oybek Akmaljon o'g'li	
KUZATUV KENGASHI XUSUSIYATLARINING KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI: NAZARIY VA KONSEPTUAL YONDASHUV.....	850
Jumayeva Go'zal Sherxon qizi	
EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH NATIJALARI NODAVLAT NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISHDA MUHIM AMALIY AHAMIYAT.....	854
Sattorov Firdavs Ziyodullayevich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIJORAT BANKLARINING O'RNI.....	858
Abduholikov Kamoldin Mahammadjonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING HUDUDLAR KESIMIDAGI RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARINI STATISTIK TAHLIL QILISH.....	862
Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA XIZMATLAR EKSPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING EKOLOGIK JIHATLARI.....	867
Qodirjonov Adxamjon Muxtorjon o'g'li	
INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNI MOLiyALASHTIRISHNING XALQARO MODELLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGI.....	872
Muxamedjanova Dilshodxon Muzaffarovna	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA "YASHIL" TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONINING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	877
Ismatulloeva Madinabonu Fozil qizi	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI MAHSULOTLARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASH	884
Kadirova L.G.	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REGION	887
Nasretdinova Farangis Odilovna	
THE IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS IN THE SERVICES SECTOR	895
Mamatkulova Shoira Djalolovna	
AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH — ICHKI TALABNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH OMILI.....	900
Mustafoev G'olib Sultonmurodovich, Abruiev Abdumalik Oynazarovich	
BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA ULARNI QO'LLASHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	906
Qarshiyeva Moxinur Olim qizi	
KORXONADA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	911
Salimova Husniya Rustamovna	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI: BUXORO VILOYATI MISOLIDA.....	918
Zayavitdinova Nafisa Muxammadovna	
XALQARO MOLIIYA INSTITUTLARI MOLIIYAVIY MAHSULOTLARI VA ULARNING O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIDAGI ROLI	926
Rasulova Dilfuza Valiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIDA IQTISODIY O'SISH VA MEHNAT BOZORI KO'RSATKICHLARINING DINAMIKASI.....	932
Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
FOYDALANUVCHI SADOQATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING MARKETING VA NEYROMARKETING MEXANIZMI SIFATIDA GEYMIKATSIIYA ELEMENTLARINI QO'LLASH: DODO PIZZA MOBIL ILOVASI MISOLIDA EMPIRIK TAHLIL	937
Yuldashev Jamshid Abrarovich, Daminova Nilufar Bahrom qizi	

KORXONADA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISHNING TASHKILIY MEKANIZMLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	945
Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ KORXONALARIDA XODIMLAR MOTIVATSIYASI VA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	948
Murodova Zilola Asatulla qizi	
KUZATILMAYDIGAN IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, SHAKLLARI, TURLARI VA YUZAGA KELISH OMILLARI.....	952
Abdullayev Shavkat Nasriddinovich	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA XARAJATLAR SMETASI VA SHTATLAR JADVALINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	959
Yaqubova Nodira Olim qizi	
РАЗВИТИЕ, РИСКИ, ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ.....	964
Бабаджанова Лола Шопулатовна, Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
KOMPANIYALARNING FOND BOZORIDAGI ISHTIROKINI RAG'BATLANTIRISH AHAMIYATI.....	970
Mamataliyev Bobur Saidnazar o'g'li	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA INTELLEKTUAL TA'MINOT ZANJIRI TEXNOLOGIYALARINING XALQARO TADBIRKORLIKDAGI O'RNI	977
Xudayberdiyev Otabek Absalomovich	
HUDUD IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYATI ORGANLARINING INSTITUTSIONAL SALOHİYATI: NAZARIY TALQIN VA YAPONIYA, GERMANIYA, XITOIY TAJRIBASI	983
Bekchanov Davron Masharipovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH VA MEHNAT FAOLIYATI UNUMDORLIGINING IQTISODIY YUKSALISHDAGI O'RNI.....	988
Anvarova Lobarxon	
TURIZM SOHASIDA HAYOT SUG'URTASI TIZIMINING IQTISODIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA MILLIY AMALIYOT	992
J.Kamalova	
MADANIYAT SOHASI MUASSASALARINI AUDITDAN O'TKAZISHNING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	999
Annayev Abdurasul Abdurashidovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA ALOQA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DAVLAT TOMONIDAN TARTIBGA SOLISH ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	1004
Nazarov Sanjar Nasridinovich	
KORXONALARDA MARKETING MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI VA AHAMIYATI (BUXORO VILOYATI KORXONALARI MISOLIDA).....	1009
Sirojov Oxunjon Odil o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA ISH BILAN BANDLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INSTITUTSIONAL VA IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI	1015
Bobojonov To'liqinbek Maxmud o'g'li	
ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALAR UCHUN RAQAMLI BOSHQARUV VA INVESTITSIYA MONITORINGINING MUALLIFLIK MODELİ	1020
Abdiyev Alimardon Chorshanbiyevich, Shamsiyeva Ruxsora Nasirovna	
IQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BUXGALTERIYA VA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI	1025
Kunduzova Kumrixon Ibragimovna, Jo'rayev Asadbek Anvarjon o'g'li	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЫ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА И ЧАСТНОГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	1031
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна	
THE ADDITIONALITY GAP: EVALUATING THE SYNERGY BETWEEN GREEN FINANCE AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN EMERGING ECONOMIES	1036
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	

АХОЛИНИ ИJTIMOИЙ НИМОЙА ҚИЛИШ ТИЗИМИДА СУН'ИЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ: О'ЗБЕКИСТОН RESPUBLIKASI MISOLIDA JORIЙ ETISH IMKONIYATLARI VA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	1042
Xidirbayev Baxrom Baxtiyarovich	
OROL BO'YI MINTAQASIDA IQLIM O'ZGARISHINING IJTIMOИЙ-IQTISODIЙ OQIBATLARI VA ZAIF AHOLI QATLAMLARIGA TA'SIRI	1047
Madenova Elmira Nzamatdinovna	
УЛУЧШЕНИЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ ЧЕРЕЗ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЮ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ: СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР	1052
Эргашев Мухиббек Аслам угли	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KIMYO SANOATI KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1057
Xaydarova Kamola Axinjanovna, Umaraliyev Asliddin Faxriddin o'g'li	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASHDA "YASHIL" LIZINGNI JORIЙ ETISH IMKONIYATLARI	1062
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
ПРЕФЕРЕНЦИИ И РИСКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА ОТ ИНИЦИАТИВЫ «ОДИН ПОЯС, ОДИН ПУТЬ»	1067
Wang Jianhong, Наров Улугбек Ирискулович	
DAVLATNING IQTISODIY SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBALARDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1071
Karimov Ulug'bek Mirzajon o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARI	1075
Quralov Nurxissa Iles o'g'li	
TURIZM SOHASIDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEХANIZMI.....	1082
Haydarov Jasur Baxodir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AUDITORLIK FAOLIYATINING ISTIQBOLLARI.....	1087
Mamatov Xabibulla Mamatovich	
O'ZBEKISTON ZIYORAT TURIZMI BRENДИNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUQADDAS QADAMJOLARNING MARKETING SALOHİYATI	1091
Turayev Ziyadulla Norsoatovich	
ASOSIY KAPITALGA YO'NALTIRILGAN INVESTISIYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MANBALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1095
Xoshimov Sobir Murtazayevich	
KREATIV IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBI, TASNIFI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.....	1103
Daminova Madinaxon Bahromjon qizi	
TURIZM TURLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSİYALASHDA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR.....	1110
Saidova Dilfuza Abdufattohovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA OBLIGATSİYALAR BOZORINING RIVOJLANISHI VA UNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	1117
Muxammedova Zarina Murodovna	
SUG'ORILADIGAN YERLARNING EKOLOGIK HOLATINI YAXSHILASHNING IQTISODIY MEХANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA JAHON TAJRIBALARI	1121
Sultonov Xudoyshukur G'ayratovich	
IQTISODIY RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH BO'YICHA ILG'OR XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	1126
Xaydarov Ravshan Xikmatullaevich	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ТОРГОВОГО БАЛАНСА УЗБЕКИСТАНА И КИТАЯ НА РАЗЛИЧНЫЕ ОТРАСЛИ.....	1131
He Xiaoqu, Уркинбаев Т. А.	
РОЛЬ ПРЯМЫХ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В РЕФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЭКОНОМИК СТРАН ПЕРЕХОДНОГО ТИПА	1135
Qian Xuanhong, Наров Улугбек Ирискулович	
"YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT"NING ULUSHINI QISQARTIRISHDA AUDITNING O'RNI	1140
Qo'shmatov Otaxon Qurbonaliyevich	

TRANSFERRING PORT MULTIMODAL COORDINATION CAPABILITIES ACROSS INSTITUTIONAL CONTEXTS: LOCALIZATION MECHANISMS IN THE CHINA-UZBEKISTAN LOGISTICS CORRIDOR.....	1146
Mu Zhendi	
TURIZM XIZMATLARINING SIFATINI OSHIRISH ORQALI MEHMONDO'STLIK INDUSTRIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	1156
Z.T. Bakayev	
ESG-ПРИНЦИПЫ В СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: ОТ ПЕРВЫХ ИНИЦИАТИВ К ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ МОДЕЛИ ОТРАСЛИ.....	1161
Аблаева Валентина Борисовна	
KAMBAG'ALLIK DARAJASINI PASAYTIRISHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH FAOLIYATINI KENGAYTIRISHNING O'RNI	1169
Saparov Murod Irgashovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH VA IQTISODIY O'SISH O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK: EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	1173
Qo'ziboyev Behzod Hamidovich	
"2025-YIL YAKUNI BO'YICHA O'ZBEKISTONDA INFLYATSIYA OMILLARI: IMF VA MARKAZIY BANK MA'LUMOTLARI TAHLILI"	1177
Ergashev E'zozbek Umirzakovich, Vaxabov A.V.	
KORXONANING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA RAQOBAT RAZVEDKASIDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	1183
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON HUDUDLARIDA AHOLI MIGRATSIYASI TAHLILI (2010-2024 YILLAR).....	1188
Hojiyev Tal'at Toshpo'latovich	
ВОПРОСЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	1192
Аман Тургунович Кенжабаев, Бахтияр Бадриддинович Садриддинов	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YASHIL IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1200
Zuxurova Nargiza Abdusattarovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IPOTEKANI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTI.....	1204
Berdinazarov Zafar Ulashovich, Xayitov Bobirbek Ergashevich	
XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MUVOFIQ IKKIYOQLAMA SOLIQQA TORTISHNI BARTARAF ETISH MEKANIZMLARINING TAHLILI.....	1212
Rajapov Shuxrat Zaripbayevich	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	1221
Sharofitdinov Shaxzod Damin o'g'li	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDA EKOLOGIK HOLAT YOMONLASHUVINING TASHQI INVESTITSIYALARGA TA'SIRI.....	1228
Poyonov Jamshid	
RAQAMLI TURIZM PLATFORMALARIDA KONTENT TAHLILI HAMDA SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	1232
Janzakov Bekzot Kulmamat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA OLIY TA'LIM SOHASIDA INVESTITSION RISKLARNI BAHOLASH TENDENSIYALARI.....	1240
Jonuzokov Mirzabek Kulmamatovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA SIRKULAR BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1246
Utegenov Ilham Baxtiyarovich	
GO'SHT YETISHTIRISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH ORQALI ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH (JIZZAX VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	1250
Otabekov Javdod Nurulla o'g'li	

O'ZBEKISTONDA TASHQI AUDIT TIZIMINING RIVOJLANISHI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	1256
Ibayev Xo'jabek, Ergashev Olloyor Furqat o'g'li	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SEPARATE SEGMENTS ... OF REGIONAL BUSINESS TOURISM	1261
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA "YASHIL" TRANSFORMATSIYANING XUSUSIYATLARI	1267
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTRON TIJORATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	1272
Babanazarova Gulzar Ziuatdinovna	
EKOLOGIK SOLIQLARNI HISOBLASH VA UN DARISH METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI YARATISH	1276
Sadullayev Rasulbek Palvanbayevich	
IQTISODIYOTDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIK SANOAT ZONALARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING IQTISODIY VA IJTIMOY AHAMIYATI	1281
Fayziyeva Iroda Shuhrat qizi	
CAPITAL ADEQUACY AND FINANCIAL STABILITY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN	1286
Shokhrukh Komilov	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA TURIZM SOHASINI STATISTIK BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI	1291
Jumanova Zilola Tuychiyevna, Sur'atova Mohiraxon Shavkat qizi	
AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANISHINI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	1296
Raximova Moxigul Isroiljonovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA HUDUDIY TAMOYILLARNING O'RNI	1300
Abduraimov Dilshod Muratkulovich	
ENHANCING STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN TOURISM SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN: A SWOT-BASED ANALYSIS	1304
Mustafakulova Sitara Shukhratovna	
SUG'URTA KOMPANIYALARIDA AXBOROT TIZIMLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH ORQALI MOLYAVIY BARQARORLIKKA ERISHISH YO'NALISHLARI	1310
Maxmudov Abduxalil Abduraxmon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON AHOLISI JINSI NISBATINING HUDUDIY VA YOSH FARQLANISHINI STATISTIK TADQIQI	1314
Toshmatov Zoyir Xudayberganovich, Begalova Durдона Baxodirovna	
MAMLAKATDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITNI YAXSHILASH ORQALI INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	1321
Roza Xudaybergenova	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINING INNOVATSION VA MOSLASHUVCHAN SHAKLLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	1326
Umarova Gulandom Tumanovna	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННО-ЧАСТНОЕ ПАРТНЕРСТВО В КОММУНАЛЬНОЙ СФЕРЕ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ОПЫТА КИТАЯ И ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИИ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	1330
Гулмаматова Дурдона Шерали кизи	
KONSTRUKTIV MASALANI YECHISH USLUBI	1334
Azimov Alisher, Sabirova Dildora, Tairova Nafisa	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОНСОЛИДИРОВАННОЙ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ	1338
Махмудова Наргиза Давлят кизи	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYALAR JARAYONIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING BUXGALTERIYA HISOBIDAGI TA'SIRI	1343
Mardonov Mamed Shavkatovich, Suyunov Raxmatillo Raximberdi o'g'li	
АНАЛИЗ И СПОСОБЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВО-ДЕЛОВОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ	1347
Ахмедова Азиза Тохириевна	

MAKROIQTISODIY TEBRANISHLAR VA IQTISODIY SIKLLAR: SABABLARI VA RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	1352
Muxammedov Murod Muxamedovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA VAZIRLIK VA IDORALARDA ICHKI AUDIT XIZMATLARI FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH VA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	1356
Ibragimova Muxlisa Abdulxakimovna	
HUDUDNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIDA TURISTIK-REKREATSION SALOHİYATNING MAZMUNI VA ILMIY TALQINI.....	1362
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ТОРГОВОГО БАЛАНСА УЗБЕКИСТАНА И КИТАЯ НА РАЗЛИЧНЫЕ ОТРАСЛИ.....	1366
He Xiaocu, Уркинбаев Т. А.	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI KREDITLASH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INSTITUTSIONAL VA MOLIYAVIY JIHATLARI TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI.....	1370
Ruziyeva Dilobar Isomjonovna, No'monova Hilola Muftillo qizi	
SUG'URTA VA FOND BOZORLARI O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO INTEGRATSIYA BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	1375
Kengesbaeva Suluxan Maxsetbay qizi	
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ЭКСПОРТА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ И ЕГО РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ РЕГИОНА.....	1380
Тулибаева Камола	
АНАЛИЗ ЛИКВИДНОСТИ БАНКОВ И ЕЁ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ФИНАНСОВУЮ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ БАНКОВСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ.....	1385
Ходжаева Феруза Авазхановна	
XORAZM VILOYATINING TASHQI SAVDO TAHLILI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	1389
Qurbanov Feruz Bahramovich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTDA INSON KAPITALINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY VAZIFALARI.....	1395
Alimova Oydin Baxtiyarovna	
OUTSOURCING: A MODERN WAY TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF ENTERPRISES.....	1402
Dauletaliyeva Aymereke Sagievna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YUK VAGONLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHNING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	1406
Kaydarov Ismatulla	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI VA INNOVATSION INFRATUZILMANING RIVOJLANISHI.....	1412
Tursunova Nazokat Tolibjonovna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK TIZIMIDA AKTIVLAR SIFATINI MUSTAQIL BAHOLASH (AQR) MARKAZINI TASHKIL ETISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1418
Suxrob G'aybulloev	
DAVLAT MOLIYAVIY NAZORATINING BUDJET MABLAG'LARIDAN OQILONA FOYDALANISHNI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI.....	1427
Kasimova Gulyor Axmatovna, Esenbayeva Biybinaz Maxmut qizi	
INNOVATSION MENEJMENT METODOLOGIYASI: NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	1432
Atamatov Abduxalil Salomovich	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIGA INVESTITSİYALARNI "CROWD INVESTING" PLATFORMALARI ORQALI JALB ETISH.....	1437
Ibragimov G'anjon G'ayratovich	
TURIZM KLASSTERLARINING EVOLUTSIYASI: AN'ANAVIY MAJMUALARDAN RAQAMLI KLASSTERLARGACHA.....	1441
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi	
IPO O'TKAZISH BOSQICHLARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI TAHLILI.....	1446
Mamatmurodov Alisher Saparboyevich	

RAQAMLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNING ZAMONAVIY BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI O'RNI.....	1455
Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmuradovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SUV RESURSLARINI SAMARALI TAQSIMLASHNING IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1463
Amanbaev Amanali Ortazbaevich	
FORECASTING THE EFFICIENCY OF SOLID WASTE RECYCLING IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.....	1467
Axmedov Sheramat Umurxojayevich	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA KICHIK BIZNES FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	1472
Toxirova Gavxaroy Tolibjon qizi	
PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN THE INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING SYSTEMS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	1477
Jumanazarov Ruzimurod, Rabbimov Elbek	

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN THE INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING SYSTEMS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article examines the institutional transformation of accounting and auditing systems in the digital economy. It highlights the role of Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, and cloud technologies, and provides a comparative analysis of global and local software solutions. The study identifies key challenges such as regulatory gaps, skills shortages, and cybersecurity risks. Scientific and practical recommendations are proposed to improve the system.

Key words: accounting, auditing, artificial intelligence, digital transformation, cybersecurity, IFRS.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary global economic landscape, the digital economy has become an integral foundation of the financial system. The rapid evolution of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data analytics, and cloud computing is fundamentally altering how enterprises operate. These processes have a direct and profound impact on accounting and auditing systems, necessitating their urgent institutional transformation. Institutional transformation implies not merely the adoption of new software, but a comprehensive redesign of regulatory frameworks, educational standards, and operational mentalities.

Global market statistics clearly illustrate the scale of this technological shift. According to Fortune Business Insights, the global accounting software market was valued at \$20.9 billion in 2025 and is projected to reach \$42.17 billion by 2032, exhibiting a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 10.5%. This exponential growth confirms the aggressive transition from traditional bookkeeping to intelligent, cloud-based ecosystems. Similarly, the Republic of Uzbekistan has gained substantial practical and theoretical experience in this domain. Significant efforts have been made to adapt 1C software to national legislation and to develop domestic solutions such as 1UZ, BEM, and UzASBO to digitalize accounting processes across both private and public sectors.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The digital transformation of accounting and auditing has been widely explored by international and domestic scholars. Adeyelu (2024) and Barri (2025) highlight the profound impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and automation in minimizing human errors and shifting traditional financial workflows. Furthermore, Musgrove (2025) and Davidson (2024) evaluate the practical benefits of leading global accounting software platforms.

Regarding local implementation, Qudbiyev (2021) and Kunduzova (2020) emphasize the critical need to transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to attract foreign investments. The practical integration of IT into Uzbekistan's accounting landscape and the CIS region is specifically analyzed by Teshaboyev (2023), Oralbaeva (2023), and Shamina & Filimonov (2018). The macroeconomic importance of ICT in Central Asia is confirmed by Shodiev et al. (2021). However, digitalization introduces severe institutional risks, such as data breaches, which are highlighted as a major financial threat in the IBM Security Report (2024).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on a systematic approach, utilizing logical and comparative analysis, induction, and deduction. A comparative functional analysis was conducted between internationally recognized accounting software (Xero, QuickBooks) and domestic platforms (UzASBO, 1UZ). Furthermore, statistical data from authoritative global research centers (IBM, Gartner, ACCA) and academic literature were synthesized to critically evaluate the institutional challenges hindering the digital transformation of the accounting and auditing sectors (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Global and Local Accounting Software Systems

Criteria	Xero / QuickBooks (Global)	UzASBO / 1UZ / BEM (Local)
Accessibility	Cloud-based with global access	Primarily local or hybrid cloud solutions
Compliance	IFRS and international standards	National tax legislation (Uzbekistan)
Functionality	Advanced analytics and AI-driven features	Basic automation and tax reporting
Integration	Bank synchronization and third-party integrations	Limited integration capabilities
Cost	Subscription-based (relatively high)	Affordable, often state-supported
Target Users	SMEs and international companies	Local businesses and government-related entities
AI Capabilities	Predictive analytics and automation	Limited implementation of AI
Real-time Reporting	Fully available	Partially available

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The automation of accounting systems dramatically enhances the speed and accuracy of financial reporting, facilitating a smoother transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). In the global market, cloud-based platforms such as "Xero," "QuickBooks Online," "FreshBooks," and "Sage Intacct" have established dominance. These platforms go beyond basic automated reporting by offering real-time bank synchronization and predictive cash-flow analysis. In Uzbekistan, "UzASBO" has shown high efficiency for budget organizations, while "1UZ" and "BEM" are heavily utilized in the private sector due to their strict compliance with the national tax code.

The integration of AI is transforming the role of the accountant. According to Gartner, AI-driven automation allows finance and accounting professionals to save an average of 5.4 hours per week by eliminating routine manual data entry. Furthermore, the "Big Four" auditing firms (Deloitte, PwC, EY, and KPMG) are investing billions into AI auditing platforms (e.g., EY Helix, KPMG Clara) to conduct real-time anomaly detection across 100% of transaction datasets, rather than relying on traditional random sampling.

Despite the clear advantages of digital technologies, the institutional transformation of accounting and auditing faces several critical hurdles:

1. Shortage of Qualified Personnel (The Skills Gap): The digital economy demands that modern accountants possess hybrid skills encompassing finance, IT, data analytics, and AI management. According to the Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA), while over 80% of finance leaders acknowledge the necessity of AI, less than 40% of organizations actively invest in upskilling their accounting staff. This creates a severe technological skills gap in the labor market.

2. Cybersecurity and Data Privacy Threats: Digital systems store massive volumes of highly sensitive financial data, making them prime targets for cyberattacks. According to IBM's Cost of a Data Breach Report, the average cost of a data breach in the financial sector has reached \$6.08 million, which is significantly higher than the global average.

3. Undeveloped Technological Infrastructure for SMEs: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) often lack the financial capital to invest in advanced Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, licensed AI audit tools, and necessary cybersecurity protocols, leaving them marginalized in the digital transformation process (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Key Challenges and Risks in the Digital Transformation of Accounting and Auditing

To systematically resolve these problems, a multi-faceted approach is required:

- **Modernization of Legislation:** Governments must adopt specialized normative acts on “Digital Accounting and Auditing” based on international standards. This includes legalizing digital evidence for audits, regulating crypto-asset accounting, and establishing clear guidelines for the use of AI in financial decision-making.
- **Educational Reform:** Higher education institutions must integrate courses such as “ERP Systems,” “AI in Accounting,” and “Financial Data Analytics” into the core curriculum of Accounting and Audit degree programs.
- **Enhancing Cybersecurity Standards:** It should be mandatory for financial data processors to comply with international security protocols (e.g., ISO/IEC 27001). The implementation of Blockchain technology can also be introduced to ensure the immutability and transparency of audit trails.
- **State Support for SMEs:** Providing tax incentives or technology grants to small businesses that implement licensed cloud accounting systems will bridge the digital divide.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTION

The automation of accounting systems and the integration of artificial intelligence serve as catalysts for unprecedented efficiency in financial management.

As demonstrated by the research, modern technological solutions accelerate transaction processing, perform deep predictive analytics, and minimize human error. However, true progress in this field requires more than just the adoption of software; it necessitates a profound institutional transformation.

Firstly, the role of the accountant is shifting from a traditional “number cruncher” to a strategic financial advisor. To support this evolution, educational systems must urgently pivot towards STEM-integrated financial training.

Secondly, regulatory bodies face the critical task of rewriting the rules of the financial ecosystem. Without a robust legal framework that recognizes smart contracts, digital assets, and AI-generated audit reports, technological advancement will outpace legal compliance, leading to market instability.

Thirdly, as cyber threats grow in sophistication and financial impact, embedding advanced cybersecurity measures into accounting infrastructure is no longer optional but a fundamental requirement for business survival.

Ultimately, addressing these institutional bottlenecks through collaborative efforts between the state, educational institutions, and the private sector will ensure a secure, transparent, and globally competitive accounting and auditing system in the era of the digital economy.

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